

Bibliometric mapping for analysing Indian research policy

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Abstract

Bibliometric techniques are used for analyzing, measuring, evaluating, and understanding the evolution and structure of science. These techniques have become mature over a period of time. Within the field of bibliometrics, evaluative bibliometrics, and science mapping are two important sub-disciplines. In evaluative bibliometrics, publication and citation data are used for measuring and evaluating quantitative aspects of the scientific activity of an individual, a research group, an organization, a country, a subject area, or a publication. In science mapping, maps are created using co-author, co-citation, or co-word analysis techniques. Science maps are visual representations of the structure and dynamics of scholarly knowledge. They aim to show how fields, disciplines, journals, scientists, publications, and scientific terms relate to each other. Science maps are called bibliometric maps when bibliometric items such as author, keywords, and affiliation are used to create science maps. This paper attempts to trace the history and development of Indian research policy using evaluative bibliometric indicators: publication count and bibliometric mapping: co-word mapping. Indian research policy publications are retrieved from the Scopus database. VosViewer is used for creating co-word maps. Though there are studies carried out on mapping specific disciplines, no study has been carried out to analyse and map research policy publications using bibliometric techniques. The findings demonstrate that the evolution and trend in Indian research policy can be traced by carrying out a comparative study of Indian research policy publications with global publications and analysis of co-word mapping created at different phases of evolution.

Introduction

Over a period, bibliometric techniques have become mature. Various disciplines indeed make use of publication and citation data for different purposes. Within the field of bibliometrics, evaluative bibliometrics, and science mapping are two important subdisciplines. In evaluative bibliometrics, scientific publications and citation data are used to measure and evaluate quantitative aspects of scientific activity, particularly research performance. Publication output and citations can be used to assess the research performance of various stakeholders, ranging from individual researchers in departments, universities, and research institutes to countries, regions, or disciplinary fields. The second stream of research is related to the mapping of scientific fields. Maps of science are called bibliometric maps when bibliometric items such as author, keywords, title words, affiliation, source title, and citation data are used for creating maps. Bibliometric maps can be created using different techniques, among which the co-author, co-citation, and co-word techniques are used prominently. Science mapping mainly aims at understanding both the structure and the evolution of scientific fields (Borner 2010; Borner, Chen and Boyack 2005; Boyak, Richard and Borner 2005; Chen 2013; Debackere and Glanzel 2004; Rafols, Porter and Leydesdorff 2010; Small 1999; Van Raan 2019).

One important advantage of science maps compared to classic reviews is that they allow non-experts to grasp easily and quickly the main features of a scientific field because they rely on the recognition of visual patterns rather than on deep scientific expertise. Therefore, they can be used as a common base among researchers, science managers, analysts, and policymakers to discuss strategic decisions, such as the allocation of resources (Borner et al. 2012; Noyons and Calero-Medina 2009).

Science maps are error-prone. For example, it is possible that they are generated based on an incorrect field delineation procedure. Also, as their production involves several technical decisions that can deeply influence the final maps, it is pivotal that such decisions and their consequences should be made transparent, to analysts and policymakers, so that science maps do not turn into “black boxes” (Rafols, Porter and Leydesdorff 2010).

Nonetheless, science maps are great tools in research policy contexts, only with a clear understanding of their limits: science maps can help decision-making, but not in providing automatic answers. From this point of view, science maps are not different from any bibliometric indicator i.e., they provide partial representations of science whose correct interpretation should take into account many different factors. Hence bibliometric indicators cannot replace peer review or evaluation by experts. In fact, bibliometric data and peer review complement each other.

In research policy, bibliometric data are mainly used to underpin the accountability and the justification of research funding allocations and to allow for the comparison of scientific input and output. However, there is a significant amount of confusion because both bibliometric indicators and research policy are ambiguous terms. In practice, the terms appear to refer to the totality of policy development and implementation, research and development (R&D) activities associated with it, including both those directly supported by the government and those supported by private sources, which are themselves considerably influenced by government policies (Brooks, H 1980).

Since research policy is related to government funding, a brief background about the Indian policy commission is given here. In India, The NITI Aayog (lit. 'Policy Commission'; abbreviation for National Institution for Transforming India) serves as the apex public policy think tank of the Government of India and the nodal agency tasked with catalysing economic development and fostering cooperative federalism through the involvement of State Governments of India in the economic policy-making process using a bottom-up approach. It was established in 2015, by the National Democratic Alliance government, to replace the Planning Commission which followed a top-down model. The Planning Commission which has a legacy of 65 years has been replaced by the NITI Aayog. The utility and significance of the Planning Commission had been questioned for a longer period. The replacement seems to be more relevant and responsive to the country's present economic needs and scenario (<https://www.niti.gov.in/>).

There have been studies conducted to analyse and trace the development in specific subject fields using science maps (Flis and van Eck 2018; Noyons and Clara Calero-Medina. 2009; Palmblad and van Eck 2018; Park and Nagy 2018; Peters and Van Raan 1993a; Peters and Van Raan 1993b; Rip and Courtial 1984; Tijssen and Van Raan 1989; Yao, Qiang et al. 2014). There is no study carried out to analyse and trace the development of research policy using bibliometric indicators. An attempt is made here to trace the history and development of Indian research policy using evaluative bibliometric indicators: publication count and bibliometric mapping: co-word mapping.

Methods

Selection of database

In any bibliometric analysis involving publications and citation data, the selection of a database is the first step. Science Citation Index Expanded, which is popularly known as Web of Science

(WOS) and Scopus are two world-leading and competing citation databases. WOS is complemented by Social Science Citation Index (SSCI) and Arts and Humanities Citation Index (AHCI). Whereas the Scopus database covers all the disciplines. The use of these two databases in the meta-analysis, research evaluation, and policy documents, is well established. There is a plethora of studies carried out comparing different features of WOS and Scopus databases (Adriaanse and Rensleigh, 2013; Bar-Ilan, 2008; Díaz et al., 2022; Erfanmanesh and Didegah, 2013; Farooq 2022; Harzing and Alakangas 2016; Pranckute 2021; Suarez et al., 2022; Zhu and Liu 2020). The databases may be used for different purposes in different fields. Both are subscribed databases and my parent institution has access to WOS and Scopus. For the present study, the Scopus database is selected because of the subject coverage as research policy publication analysis comprises all the disciplines: science, technology, medicine, social science, arts, and humanities. A search carried out for the same search strategy on 18th November 2022 on both databases, retrieved 714,385 records on Scopus and 149,679 records on WOS.

Search strategy construction and publications retrieval

The construction of a comprehensive search strategy to retrieve all the publications related to Research Policy is very crucial. The search strategy should include all the synonymous terms and abbreviations used to describe Research Policy. The search strategy was constructed after doing several iterations of the search for Research Policy, and by going through the author keywords and indexed keywords, about 78 search terms were selected which include not only synonyms for Research Policy, but also specific types of policy and terms related to different stages of policy implementation.

The search strategy is given below:

("reform* policy") OR ("policy reform*") OR ("policy design*") OR ("design* policy") OR ("policy making") OR ("policy implement*") OR ("policy analysis") OR ("policy evaluat*") OR ("policy efficacy") OR ("policy impact") OR ("policy regulation") OR ("policy effectiveness") OR ("policy standard") OR ("policy quality") OR ("policy planning") OR ("science policy") OR ("research policy") OR ("public policy") OR ("government policy") OR ("institution* policy") OR ("organization* policy") OR ("social policy") OR ("economic policy") OR ("technology policy") OR ("innovation policy") OR ("social policy") OR ("economic policy") OR ("political policy") OR ("development policy") OR ("health policy") OR ("data policy") OR ("technolog* policy") OR ("innovation policy") OR ("sustainability policy") OR ("education policy") OR ("wom?n policy") OR ("gender policy") OR ("mobility policy") OR ("transportation policy") OR ("labour policy") OR ("labor policy") OR ("environment* policy") OR ("energy policy") OR ("ethnic policy") OR ("media policy") OR ("financial policy") OR ("banking policy") OR ("cultural policy") OR ("agriculture policy") OR ("marketing policy") OR ("leasing policy") OR ("fiscal policy") OR ("water policy") OR ("trade policy") OR ("climate policy") OR ("land policy") OR ("building policy") OR ("monetary policy") OR ("food policy") OR ("foreign policy") OR ("textile policy") OR ("fisheries policy") OR ("defence policy") OR ("housing policy") OR ("employment policy") OR ("decarbonisation policy") OR ("military policy") OR ("industrial policy") OR ("child policy") OR ("female policy") OR ("male policy") OR ("forest policy") OR ("wildlife policy") OR ("conservation policy") OR ("sports policy") OR ("entertainment policy") OR ("marine policy") OR ("urban policy")

The search was carried out on 18th November 2022. The search was limited to search terms appearing in the Title, Abstract, and Keywords. Retrieved 714,385 publications out of which 1157 were deleted from the 'erratum' document type, as these are not research papers. This resulted in 713,228 publications for analysis. Out of these 15,560 publications were identified

as Indian publications, i.e. publications having the term ‘India’ in at least one of the author affiliations. Since affiliations are rendered in a standard format in the publications, there is no ambiguity in retrieving publications containing ‘India’ in the affiliation field. Retrieved Indian publications were downloaded with bibliographic details i.e., title, abstract, author, citation, publication year, author-assigned keywords, and indexed keywords in tab-delimited text file format, suitable for further processing.

Software tool for generating co-word map

VOSviewer is a software tool for constructing and visualizing bibliometric maps or bibliometric networks, in which VOS stands for visualization of similarities. This software tool can create co-author networks, citation networks, co-word networks, and co-occurrence networks based on data downloaded from various databases, including Scopus. Visualizations of bibliometric networks can be explored in full detail using zoom and scroll functionality. Density visualizations provide a quick overview of the main areas in a bibliometric network. Overlay visualizations can for instance be used to show developments over time. State-of-the-art techniques for network layout and network clustering are provided. Layout and clustering results can be fine-tuned using various parameters. A number of advanced features are available for creating bibliometric networks (e.g., co-authorship, bibliographic coupling, and co-citation networks). For instance, the influence of publications with many authors, many citations, or many references can be reduced using a fractional counting approach. Data cleaning can be performed using thesaurus files. (Van Eck and Waltman 2010, 2014; <https://www.vosviewer.com/features/highlights>). For the present study, VOSViewer version 1.6.18 is used for generating co-word maps.

Analysis and discussion

The analysis is carried out in two parts: (1) Comparative publication analysis of Global ‘research policy’ publications and Indian ‘research policy’ publications in terms of affiliation, authors, collaborating countries, funding sponsors, document types, growth of publications, subject coverage, and source publications. (2) Co-word map analysis to visualize the evolution and trend of Indian research policy.

Publication analysis

Following is a comparison of global and Indian contributions in terms of top 10 affiliations, authors, collaborating countries, funding sponsors, and source of publication. A comparative analysis of document type, subject coverage, and year-wise publication is also given.

According to the retrieved publications, the first Indian publication is by Mukerjee, R from the University of Lucknow, India: Mukerjee. R. New approaches to population; 1941; Social Forces;20(2)141-146.

Comparative analysis of top 10 affiliations

From Table 1 it is observed that all top 10 Global and Indian affiliations are academic institutions. Looking at the percentage contribution, a smaller number of Indian academic institutions are contributing compared to Global contributions.

Table 1: Top 10 affiliations in global and Indian publications

<i>TOP 10 GLOBAL AFFILIATIONS</i>	<i># Publ</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>TOP 10 AFFILIATIONS IN INDIAN PUBLICATIONS</i>	<i># Publ</i>	<i>%</i>
University of Toronto	4682	0.66	Jawaharlal Nehru University	588	3.78
University of Oxford	4605	0.65	University of Delhi	378	2.43

University College London	3904	0.55	Indian Institute of Technology Delhi	319	2.05
Chinese Academy of Sciences	3692	0.52	Public Health Foundation of India	281	1.81
London School of Economics and Political Science	3670	0.52	Indian Institute of Technology Kharagpur	268	1.72
University of California, Berkeley	3595	0.5	Organisation Mondiale de la Santé	227	1.49
University of Melbourne	3561	0.5	Indian Institute of Technology Bombay	218	1.4
University of Cambridge	3510	0.49	London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine	198	1.27
The University of Sydney	3505	0.49	All India Institute of Medical Sciences, New Delhi	192	1.23
The Australian National University	3443	0.48	Jadavpur University	177	1.14n

Top 10 contributing authors

From Table 2, it is interesting to note that among the top 10 contributors in Indian publications, only Tiwari A.K., Shukla. P.R. and Prabhakaran.D. have Indian affiliations, indicating that India is highly collaborating with other countries. Also, the majority of them belong to Health Sector. Also, the top 10 global contributors account for 0.31% of total publications, whereas the top 10 Indian contributors account for 2.7% of total Indian publications. The following list gives the latest affiliation of the top 10 contributors:

Table 2. Top 10 Authors in global and Indian publications

<i>TOP 10 AUTHORS: GLOBAL</i>	<i># Publ</i>	<i>TOP 10 AUTHORS: INDIAN PUBLICATIONS</i>	<i># Publ</i>
Anon Conselleria de Sanitat Universal i Salut Pública, Valencia, Spain	524	Kalantar-Zadeh, K., Univ of California, Irvine,CA, US	48
McKee, M. London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine, London, UK	206	Saadi, G., Faculty of Medicine, Cairo Univ Giza, Egypt	45
Sovacool, B.K. Aarhus Universitet, Aarhus, Denmark	204	Ulasi, I. College of Medicine, Univ of Nigeria, Ituku-Ozalla, Nigeria	45
Howlett, M. Simon Fraser University, Burnaby, Canada	203	Liakopoulos, V. Division of Nephrology and Hypertension, AHEPA Hospital, Aristotle Univ of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, Greece	44
Lin, B. Xiamen University, Xiamen, China	200	Tiwari, A.K. Rajagiri Business School, Rajagiri Valley Campus, Kochi, India	44
Wagner, L. Affiliation not available	194	Lui, S.F. Division of Health System, Policy and Management, Jockey Club School of Public Health and Primary Care, Chinese Univ of Hong Kong, Hong Kong	42
Nijkamp, P. Mohammed VI Polytechnic University, Ben Guerir, Morocco	181	Balducci, A. Italian Kidney Foundation, Rome, Italy	41

Snow, N. Affiliation not available	177	Tantisattamo, E. Division of Nephrology Hypertension and Kidney Transplantation, Department of Medicine, Univ of California Irvine School of Medicine, Orange, CA, US	41
Gupta, R. University of Pretoria, Pretoria, South Africa	169	Shukla, P.R. Ahmedabad Univ, Ahmedabad, India	39
Shahbaz, M. Beijing Institute of Technology, Beijing, China	140	Prabhakaran, D. Public Health Foundation India, New Delhi, India	36

Top 10 contributing/collaborating countries

India is in 12th place among global contributing countries. A comparison of countries with which India is collaborating and the top 10 global contributing countries as given in Table 3, reveals that India is collaborating with South Africa and Switzerland which are not there in the top 10 global contributing countries and are in 14th place, and 16th place respectively. While countries with which India is collaborating Italy and Brazil occupy 11th place and 13th place respectively. Fig 1. and Fig 2 give the geographical distribution of the top 10 global contributing countries and the top 10 countries with which India is collaborating. These graphs are created using Microsoft Power Map for Excel.

Table 3: Top 10 contributing/collaborating countries

<i>COUNTRY: GLOBAL</i>	<i># Publ</i>	<i>COUNTRY: INDIAN</i>	<i># Publ</i>
United States	190267	United States	1772
United Kingdom	90233	United Kingdom	1235
China	42447	Australia	645
Australia	37167	Canada	458
Canada	33557	China	422
Germany	29712	Germany	364
Netherlands	21413	South Africa	361
Italy	20548	Switzerland	341
France	20105	Netherlands	303
Brazil	19447	France	296

Fig 1. Geographical distribution of global contributing countries

Fig 2. Geographical distribution of countries with which India is collaborating

Funding sponsors analysis

It is interesting to note that none of the top 10 global funding sponsors, sponsor Indian projects, as given in table 4. Also, it is interesting to note that under global sponsors, a large number of publications are sponsored by the National Natural Science Foundation of China.

Table 4: Top 10 Funding sponsors

<i>FUNDING SPONSOR: GLOBAL</i>	<i># Publ</i>	<i>FUNDING SPONSOR: INDIAN</i>	<i># Pub</i>
National Natural Science Foundation of China	13404	Dept of S & T Ministry of S & T, India	172
National Science Foundation	6270	Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation	147
Europeanmission	5926	University Grants Commission	106
Economic and Social Research Council	4953	Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, India	89
National Institutes of Health	4229	Wellcome Trust	75
Seventh Framework Programme	3084	Indian Council of Medical Research	69
Horizon 2020 Framework Programme	3017	World Health Organization	68
Fundamental Research Funds for the Central Universities	2389	National Institutes of Health	66
Conselho Nacional de Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico	2344	Science and Engineering Research Board	66
Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council of Canada	2158	World Bank Group	65

Publication type distribution analysis

Table 5 gives publication type distribution for both global and India. The same is represented in the pie chart in Fig 3 and Fig 4. It is observed that Indian publications have all document type covered and is almost the same as the global contribution, except that India has about 6.8% less article contribution; 2.41% more Review contribution, and 4.48% more conference paper contribution.

Table 5: Publication type distribution

<i>DOC TYPE: GLOBAL</i>	<i># Publ</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>DOC TYPE: INDIAN</i>	<i># Publ</i>	<i>%</i>
Article	510218	71.54	Article	10074	64.74
Review	56260	7.89	Conf Paper	1801	11.57
Conf Paper	50020	7.01	Review	1604	10.3
Book Chap	41461	5.81	Book Chap	1064	6.83
Book	16540	2.32	Book	382	2.46
Note	14270	2	Note	243	1.56
Editorial	12008	1.68	Editorial	174	1.12
Short Survey	5638	0.79	Letter	157	1.01
Letter	5395	0.75	Short Survey	53	0.34
Conf Review	943	0.13	Data Paper	5	0.03
Retracted	217	0.03	Abstract Report	1	0.01
Data Paper	122	0.02	Undefined	2	0.01
Report	53	0.01			
Business Article	12	0.001			
Abstract Report	11	0.001			
Undefined	60	0.001			

Fig 3. Documents by type: Global

Fig 4. Document type: India

Source publication analysis

It is observed that the top 10 source titles are both Indian and foreign source titles.

Table 6: Top 10 source publication

<i>SOURCE TITLE: GLOBAL</i>	<i># Publ</i>	<i>SOURCE TITLE: INDIAN</i>	<i># Publ</i>
Energy Policy	7916	Economic And Political Weekly	356
Sustainability Switzerland	5752	Energy Policy	244
International Journal Of Environmental Research And Public Health	3410	Indian Journal Of Labour Economics	148
Social Science And Medicine	2525	Renewable And Sustainable Energy Reviews	138
Journal Of Cleaner Production	2451	Materials Today Proceedings	85
Plos One	2092	Current Science	84
Marine Policy	2052	Lancet	82
Energy	1949	International Studies	81
Renewable And Sustainable Energy Reviews	1942	Lecture Notes In Electrical Engineering	80
Science	1928	Journal Of Cleaner Production	79

Subject-wise publication distribution analysis

Table 7 gives subject-wise publication distribution of Global and Indian contributions. A comparison of subject-wise contribution shows that India contributes more in the subject areas: Biochemistry, Genetics, and Molecular Biology; Business, Dentistry; Management and Accounting; Chemical Engineering; Chemistry; Computer Science; Decision Sciences; Economics, Econometrics, and Finance; Energy; Engineering; Environmental Science; Immunology and Microbiology; Materials Science; Mathematics; Pharmacology, Toxicology, and Pharmaceuticals; Physics and Astronomy. However, India contributes less in the subject areas: Arts and Humanities; Health Professions; Neuroscience; Nursing; Psychology; Social Sciences

Table 7: Subject-wise publication distribution

<i>SUBJECT AREA</i>	<i># Publ: GLOBAL</i>	<i>%</i>	<i># Publ: INDIAN</i>	<i>%</i>
Agricultural and Biological Sciences	35649	5	889	5.71
Arts and Humanities	44854	6.3	460	2.96
Biochemistry, Genetics and Molecular Biology	10679	1.49	422	2.71
Business, Management and Accounting	67647	9.48	1891	12.15
Chemical Engineering	7117	0.99	324	2.08
Chemistry	4657	0.65	210	1.34
Computer Science	32334	4.53	1545	9.93
Decision Sciences	12594	1.77	483	3.11
Dentistry	2097	0.29	48	0.31
Earth and Planetary Sciences	30353	4.26	585	3.76
Economics, Econometrics and Finance	99476	13.95	2492	16.02
Energy	52062	7.3	2027	13.02
Engineering	69912	9.8	2518	16.18
Environmental Science	130811	18.34	3100	19.92
Health Professions	6022	0.84	76	0.49
Immunology and Microbiology	4333	0.61	165	1.06
Materials Science	6386	0.89	367	2.35
Mathematics	14540	2.04	524	3.37
Medicine	164902	23.12	2924	18.79
Multidisciplinary	9438	1.32	280	1.8
Neuroscience	2209	0.31	29	0.19
Nursing	24685	3.46	188	1.21
Pharmacology, Toxicology and Pharmaceutics	5037	0.71	180	1.16
Physics and Astronomy	5179	0.73	300	1.93
Psychology	17261	2.42	222	1.43
Social Sciences	287775	40.34	4889	31.42
Veterinary	2002	0.28	47	0.3
Undefined	972	0.14	0	

Year-wise publication distribution analysis

Table 8a and Table 8b give publication distribution of global and Indian publications respectively. The same is represented in graph form in Fig 5 and Fig 6 respectively. As seen in the tables and graphs, the publication distribution can be divided into 3 phases. Phase 1: publications up to 2000: infancy period: slowly increasing, maybe because techniques related to policy analysis and implementation were not developed. Phase 2: 2001-2015: slow development period: slow increase in publications, because of the developing stage of techniques. Phase 3: 2016-2022: rapid growth in publications, because of mature and well-developed techniques related to policy analysis and implementation. The initiation of the NITI planning commission by the Indian government in 2015 may also be a reason for the Indian publications steep increase after 2015.

Table 8a: Year-wise publication distribution: Global

<i>Year</i>	<i># Publ</i>	<i>YEAR</i>	<i>#Publ</i>	<i>Year</i>	<i># Publ</i>	<i>Year</i>	<i># Publ</i>	<i>Year</i>	<i># Publ</i>
2023	290	1999	8431	1974	896	1949	35	1924	9
2022	40092	1998	8485	1973	752	1948	24	1923	7
2021	48222	1997	7764	1972	455	1947	23	1922	4
2020	43575	1996	7706	1971	336	1946	20	1921	4
2019	40791	1995	7212	1970	305	1945	23	1920	2
2018	37579	1994	6923	1969	253	1944	27	1919	3
2017	35523	1993	7184	1968	199	1943	26	1918	4
2016	32360	1992	5927	1967	152	1942	20	1917	2
2015	30375	1991	5791	1966	154	1941	27	1916	7
2014	29910	1990	5278	1965	143	1940	17	1915	2
2013	28929	1989	4484	1964	117	1939	18	1914	3
2012	27416	1988	4162	1963	111	1938	23	1913	2
2011	24982	1987	3559	1962	97	1937	18	1912	1
2010	22971	1986	3295	1961	67	1936	16	1911	1
2009	21379	1985	3538	1960	79	1935	16	1909	2
2008	19663	1984	3431	1959	69	1934	8	1908	2
2007	18495	1983	3174	1958	54	1933	11	1907	1
2006	17459	1982	3159	1957	55	1932	9	1904	1
2005	16733	1981	2556	1956	43	1931	9	1903	1
2004	15268	1980	2564	1955	52	1930	9	1901	3
2003	14056	1979	2444	1954	30	1929	6	1900	3
2002	10912	1978	1868	1953	47	1928	7	1897	2
2001	9607	1977	1399	1952	59	1927	5	1896	1
2000	9049	1976	1194	1951	44	1926	6	1855	1
		1975	983	1950	36	1925	5		

Table 8b: Year-wise publication distribution: Indian

<i>Year</i>	<i># Publ</i>	<i>Year</i>	<i># Publ</i>	<i>Year</i>	<i># Publ</i>
2023	25	2002	152	1981	17
2022	1765	2001	116	1980	8
2021	1904	2000	106	1979	1
2020	1495	1999	73	1978	7
2019	1259	1998	94	1977	2
2018	1136	1997	58	1976	3
2017	944	1996	65	1975	3
2016	901	1995	63	1974	4
2015	780	1994	47	1973	4
2014	653	1993	34	1972	2
2013	581	1992	16	1971	1
2012	530	1991	33	1970	1
2011	419	1990	25	1968	1
2010	379	1989	21	1967	3

2009	330	1988	22	1966	5
2008	319	1987	12	1965	2
2007	285	1986	17	1964	2
2006	217	1985	18	1963	1
2005	167	1984	19	1961	4
2004	188	1983	9	1960	4
2003	198	1982	8	1956	1
				1941	1

Fig 5. Publication distribution: Global

Fig 6. Publication distribution: India

Co-word map analysis

To visualize the evolution and trend of Indian research policy, co-word maps are used and created using VOSviewer software. The retrieved Indian research policy publications data set is divided into 8 parts by dates, which makes it easy to understand historical developments and to analyse and identify recent trends. The three phases are as given in section 3.1.8. The last phase viz. 2016-2023 is again divided into 6 sets to analyse pre-pandemic and post-pandemic effects on research policy. The following are the subsets considered for analysis:

1. 1941-2000;
2. 2001-2015;
3. 2016-2017;
4. 2018;
5. 2019;
6. 2020;
7. 2021;
8. 2022.

In VOSviewer option for selecting both author-assigned keywords and indexed keywords is considered. The average number of keywords per publication is used as the threshold value. Subsequently, unrelated words were eliminated (i.e., regional words, organization names, generic terms) and merged repetitive words (i.e., singular and plural forms, and abbreviation and full name) by using a stop word list. Default values for attraction and repulsion are selected.

With the list of keywords, VOSviewer generated the co-occurrence map and clustered the keywords based on the co-occurrences. Two words are defined as co-occurred if they appear in the same document. Finally, the scientific landscape is generated. In this map, the size and colour of the circle represent the frequency of occurrence and cluster type of the individual keyword, respectively. Lastly, the distance between the keywords is representative of their relative co-occurrence, e.g., two keywords that are close to each other co-occur more frequently, whereas a large distance between two keywords indicates that they do not co-occur. Table 9 gives the parameters used to create co-word maps. Table 10 gives cluster details for each data

set. Here cluster numbers are given based on the cluster size in ascending order. Based on the terms and their total link strength occurring in each cluster, each cluster is manually assigned a name. Table 11 gives the comparison of clusters formed in 8 data sets.

VOSViewer generates three types of maps: Network visualization, Overlay visualization, and Density visualization. For viewing cluster formation and their relation, Density visualization is preferred. Hence in this paper for all 8 subsets, a Density visualization map is given. However, VOSviewer facilitates the Network visualisation of maps online. An online link to view Network visualisation maps for all 8 data subsets is given.

Analysis of data set 1941-2000

As given in Table 9, in this data set, 3174 keywords are extracted from 817 publications. A total of 340 keywords meet the threshold value of 4. A default value of 2 for attraction and 0 for repulsion is selected. Figure 7 gives a density visualisation of the map generated. This can be viewed online at: <https://tinyurl.com/2fsxjy43>

As given in Table 10, according to cluster size, the 6 clusters formed are 1. Health; 2. Energy; 3. Rural area, Employment, Trade, Technology; 4. Environmental protection; Environmental impact; 5. Social policy; 6. Information science

Analysis of data set 2001-2015

As given in Table 9, in this data set, 23637 keywords are extracted from 5322 publications. A total of 1000 keywords are selected with the largest total link strength and meeting the threshold value of 4. A default value of 2 for attraction and 0 for repulsion is selected. Figure 8 gives a density visualisation of the map generated. This can be viewed online at: <https://tinyurl.com/2fr8woza>

As given in Table 10, according to cluster size, the 3 clusters formed are 1. Health; 2. Climate change; Environment; Economic growth; 3. Energy; Renewable energy; Sustainable development

Analysis of data set 2016-2017

As given in Table 9, in this data set, 11968 keywords are extracted from 1845 publications. A total of 550 keywords meet the threshold value of 7. A default value of 2 for attraction and 0 for repulsion is selected. Figure 9 gives a density visualisation of the map generated. This can be viewed online at: <https://tinyurl.com/2ewx3g7u>

As given in Table 10, according to cluster size, the 4 clusters formed are 1. Health; 2. Sustainable development; Economics; Climate change; 3. Energy; Solar energy; Fossil fuel; 4.: Air pollution; Waste management.

Analysis of data set 2018

As given in Table 9, in this data set, 8703 keywords are extracted from 1136 publications. A total of 268 keywords meet the threshold value of 8. A default value of 2 for attraction and 0 for repulsion is selected. Figure 10 gives a density visualisation of the map generated. This can be viewed online at: <https://tinyurl.com/2m5q5wft>

As given in Table 10, according to cluster size, the 5 clusters formed are 1. Health; 2. Climate change; 3. Energy; Renewable energy resources; Sustainable development; 4. Public policy; 5. Fiscal policy; Monetary policy

Analysis of data set 2019

As given in Table 9, in this data set, 9238 keywords are extracted from 1259 publications. A total of 319 keywords meet the threshold value of 7. A default value of 2 for attraction and 0 for repulsion is selected. Figure 11 gives a density visualisation of the map generated. This can be viewed online at: <https://tinyurl.com/2nv5xana>

As given in Table 10, according to cluster size, the 4 clusters formed are 1. Health 2. Climate change; Environmental policy; 3. Energy; Sustainable development; Fossil fuel; 4. Public policy

Analysis of data set 2020

As given in Table 9, in this data set, 11528 keywords are extracted from 1495 publications. A total of 367 keywords meet the threshold value of 8. A default value of 2 for attraction and 0 for repulsion is selected. Figure 12 gives a density visualisation of the map generated. This can be viewed online at: <https://tinyurl.com/2qkezssw>

As given in Table 10, according to cluster size, the 4 clusters formed are 1. Health; Coronavirus; 2. Environmental policy; Climate change 3. Energy; Renewable energy resources 4. Sustainable development; Public policy

Analysis of data set 2021

As given in Table 9, in this data set, 13583 keywords are extracted from 1904 publications. A total of 640 keywords meet the threshold value of 7. A default value of 2 for attraction and 0 for repulsion is selected. Figure 13 gives a density visualisation of the map generated. This can be viewed online at: <https://tinyurl.com/2zggpcmjnm>

As given in Table 10, according to cluster size, the 4 clusters formed are 1. Health; Coronavirus; 2. Climate change; Environmental policy; Ecosystem; Environmental protection; 3. Energy; Sustainable development; Renewable energy; Economics; Solar energy; 4. Economic growth

Analysis of data set 2022

As given in Table 9, in this data set, 12982 keywords are extracted from 1790 publications. A total of 536 keywords meet the threshold value of 7. A default value of 2 for attraction and 0 for repulsion is selected. Figure 14 gives a density visualisation of the map generated. This can be viewed online at: <https://tinyurl.com/2flkc8su>

As given in Table 10, according to cluster size, the 5 clusters formed are 1. Coronavirus; Health; 2. Climate change; Environmental policy; Sustainability; 3. Energy; Renewable energy; Fossil fuels 4. Economics; Alternative energy; 5. Sustainable development

Growth and trend in Indian research policy

Based on the Total link strength of the nodes in each cluster, the top 3 clusters in 8 data sets are identified, which is given in Table 12. From this, we observe that Energy policy occurs in all 8 data sets. Health policy occurs in the first 7 data sets, 1941-2022, with coronavirus occurring in 2020 and 2021. Climate change in 2001-2019 and 2021; Sustainable development in 2001-2017; 2020-2022.

However, this is only a preliminary study. A more detailed map reading has to be done to get more insight into the growth and development of research policy, taking into consideration Intra and Inter-links of the nodes in each cluster.

Table 9. Parameters used to create a co-word map

<i>Year</i>	<i># Publ</i>	<i># Keywords</i>	<i>Threshold</i>	<i># Keywords selected</i>	<i># Clusters</i>	<i>Attn/Repn</i>
1941-2000	817	3174	4	340	6	2/0
2001-2015	5322	23637	4	1000	3	2/0
2016-2017	1845	11968	7	550	4	2/0
2018	1136	8703	8	268	5	2/0
2019	1259	9238	7	319	4	2/0
2020	1495	11528	8	367	4	2/0
2021	1904	13583	7	640	4	2/0
2022	1790	12982	7	536	5	2/0

Table 10: Cluster details of data sets

<i>Year/Cluster #</i>	<i># Items</i>	<i>Top 4% TLS Terms</i>	<i>TLS</i>
1941-2000			
C1. Health	136	health policy; organization and management; female; Asia; education	73; 36; 34; 27; 26
C2. Energy	86	public policy; energy policy; economics	117; 93; 52
C3. Employment; Trade; Poverty	45	developing country; rural area; employment; trade policy; poverty alleviation	152; 19;14;12;10
C4. Environment	40	environmental protection; environmental impact	41; 24
C5. Social policy	30	social policy	32
C6. Information science	3	information services	4
2001-2015			
C1. Health	444	health policy; female; policy; male; public health; adult; health program; health care delivery; organisation and management; government;	806; 340; 261;258; 232; 198; 180; 175; 173; 141
C2. Climate change; Environment; Economic growth	308	Asia; south Asia; Eurasia; policy making; climate change; environmental policy; sustainability; economic growth; China; policy implementation	478; 420; 411; 304; 221; 173; 125; 121; 114; 110
C3. Energy; Renewable energy; Sustainable development	248	energy policy; public policy; developing country; economics; sustainable development; rural area; decision making; energy efficiency; renewable energy resources; energy utilisation	672; 504; 393; 276; 256; 153; 147; 129; 115; 103
2016-2017			
C1. Health	218	health policy; female; male; adult; government; public health; health care delivery; procedures; organisation and management	189; 113; 87; 76; 68; 68; 59; 59; 53
C2. Sustainable development; Economics; Climate change	161	sustainable development; developing country; economics; policy making; climate change; decision making	103; 102; 100; 97; 85; 67

C3. Energy; Solar energy; Fossil fuel	135	energy policy; renewable energy resources; solar energy; fossil fuel; energy efficiency	299; 90; 64; 63; 58
C4. Air pollution; Waste management	36	air pollution; waste management	22; 21
2018			
C1. Health	92	health policy; economics; female; adult	116; 72; 62; 50
C2. Climate change	86	climate change; developing country; policy making	67; 67; 56
C3. Energy; Renewable energy resources; Sustainable development	77	energy policy; renewable energy resources; sustainable development	216; 60; 59
C4. Public policy	6	public policy	53
C5. Fiscal policy; Monetary policy	3	income; fiscal policy; monetary policy	16; 10; 8
2019			
C1. Health	122	health policy; female; male; adult; controlled study	116; 96; 75; 60; 48
C2. Climate change; Environmental policy	81	climate change; environmental policy; policy making	59; 49; 45
C3. Energy; Sustainable development; Fossil fuel	68	energy policy; sustainable development; fossil fuel	186; 84; 51
C4. Public policy	48	public policy; developing country	76; 67
2020			
C1. Health; Coronavirus	143	health policy; coronavirus; female; adult; public health; male	140; 99; 83; 69; 69; 67
C2. Environmental policy; Climate change	94	policy making; environmental policy; climate change; developing country	83; 78; 72; 65
C3. Energy; Renewable energy resources	79	energy policy; renewable energy; renewable energy resources	235; 60; 57
C4. Sustainable development; Public policy	50	sustainable development; public policy	92; 91
2021			
C1. Health; Coronavirus	229	health policy; coronavirus; public health; female; pandemic; public policy; male; adult; epidemiology	236; 219; 133; 126; 117; 113; 99; 95; 74
C2. Climate change; Environmental policy; Ecosystem;	209	policy making; climate change; environmental policy; sustainability; nonhuman; policy implementation; ecosystem; environmental protection	107; 95; 85; 80; 42; 42; 39; 38

Environmental protection			
C3. Energy; Sustainable development; Renewable energy; Economics; Solar energy	155	energy policy; sustainable development; renewable energy; economics; decision making; solar energy	266; 119; 67; 61; 60; 60
C4. Economic growth	45	developing country; economic growth	85; 34
2022			
C1. Coronavirus; Health	161	Coronavirus; health policy; public policy; female; pandemic; adult	159; 144; 110; 91; 83; 70
C2. Climate change; Environmental policy; Sustainability	125	climate change; policy-making; environmental policy; sustainability; environmental protection	92; 89; 73; 71; 49
C3. Energy; Renewable energy; Fossil fuels	113	energy policy; renewable energy; fossil fuels; renewable energy resources	331; 96; 78; 68
C4. Economics; Alternative energy	89	developing country; economics; alternative energy	286; 250; 206
C5. Sustainable development	48	sustainable development; decision making	344; 257

Table 11. Comparison of cluster formation in 8 data sets

	<i>C1</i>	<i>C2</i>	<i>C3</i>	<i>C4</i>	<i>C5</i>	<i>C6</i>
1941-2000	Health	Energy	Rural area, Employment, Trade, Technology	Environmental protection; Environmental impact	Social policy	Information science
2001-2015	Health	Climate change; Environment; Economic growth	Energy; Renewable energy; Sustainable development			
2016-2017	Health	Sustainable development; Economics; Climate change	Energy; Solar energy; Fossil fuel	Air pollution; Waste management		
2018	Health	Climate change	Energy; Renewable energy resources; Sustainable development	Public policy	Fiscal policy; Monetary policy	

2019	Health	Climate change; Environmental policy	Energy; Sustainable development; Fossil fuel	Public policy		
2020	Health; Coronavirus	Environmental policy; Climate change	Energy; Renewable energy resources	Sustainable development; Public policy		
2021	Health; Coronavirus	Climate change; Environmental policy; Ecosystem; Environmental protection;	Energy; Sustainable development; Renewable energy; Economics; Solar energy;	Economic growth		
2022	Coronavirus; Health	Climate change; Environmental policy; Sustainability	Energy; Renewable energy; Fossil fuels	Economics; Alternative energy	Sustainable development	

Table 12. Top 3 clusters in 8 data sets

<p>1941-2000: (6 clusters)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Developing country; Rural area; Employment 2. Public policy; Energy policy 3. Health Policy 	<p>2019: (4 clusters)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Energy Policy 2. Health policy 3. Climate change; Environmental policy; Policy making
<p>2001-2015: (3 clusters)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Health Policy 2. Energy policy; Public policy; Developing country; Economics; Sustainable development 3. Asia; South Asia; Policy making; Climate change 	<p>2020: (4 clusters)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Energy policy 2. Health policy; Coronavirus 3. Sustainable development; Public policy
<p>2016-2017: (4 clusters)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Energy Policy 2. Health policy 3. Sustainable development; Developing country; Economics; Policy making; Climate change 	<p>2021: (4 clusters)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Health policy; Coronavirus 2. Energy policy; Sustainable development 3. Policy making; Climate change

related to policy analysis and implementation were not developed. Phase 2: 2001-2015: slow development period: slow increase in publications, because of the developing stage of techniques. Phase 3: 2016-2022: rapid growth in publications, because of mature and well-developed techniques related to policy analysis and implementation.

For the generation of co-word maps, the third phase is further divided into six phases: pre-pandemic, pandemic, and post-pandemic phases. Using co-word mapping, scientific landscapes are visualized for 8 data sets, grouped based on the growth of publications. Clusters formed in each dataset were analyzed and assigned keywords describing the cluster. Hence large data sets could be easily grouped into meaningful small clusters and hence development and trend could be visualised easily. Based on the Total link strength of the nodes in each cluster, the top 3 clusters in 8 data sets are identified, which is given in Table 12. From this, we observe that Energy policy occurs in all 8 data sets. Health policy occurs in the first 7 data sets, 1941-2022, with coronavirus occurring in 2020 and 2021. Climate change in 2001-2019 and 2021; Sustainable development in 2001-2017; 2020-2022.

This preliminary study is successful in demonstrating bibliometric indicators in general and bibliometric maps, in particular, can be used to visualize scientific landscapes. Due to time constraints, only major nodes in each cluster are considered. A deeper study of the maps must be carried out by looking at each node and the links generated to connect to other nodes. This will give more insights into the growth and trend in the subject field. The findings demonstrate that bibliometric techniques for research evaluation have reached the stage where they can be used as a management tool in research policy-making. However, research output statistics should never be allowed completely to determine scientific decision-making. They constitute only one of several inputs that need to be considered. Such statistics certainly, do not remove the need for the peer-review process, but offers the prospect of helping enhance their effectiveness in the future, provided they are interpreted with care.

Limitations

This study is limited to the publications retrieved from the SCOPUS database. Hence it may not provide a complete research policy landscape visualization. The maps are created using VOSviewer software. Cluster formation and link generation depend on the type of algorithm used in the software.

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